

GIANTLEAP

DELIVERABLE D5.4

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Fuel-cell system
assembled and
commissioned

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Abstract: This deliverable tackles the assembly of the system with regards to choice of components and packaging. BEG has designed and engineered a system around two ElringKlinger stacks to fit in the VDL trailer. In this report, a component walkthrough can be found with respective positioning and reasoning. Additionally, the conditioning and commissioning of the system is described, including first tests and the reference point for Beginning of Life (BoL).

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1 Introduction

1.1 Document Overview

The objective for the work package 5 is defined in the Giantleap proposal as follows:

WP5: Fuel Cell Systems will integrate the full-size stacks together with BoP components into a full-fledged FC system, which will then be integrated further in a range extender for battery buses.

1.2 Background and Project Context

The aim of the project is to develop a Fuel Cell System used as a range extender for battery buses. The project context can be described in connected relationships between the different work packages one through six. Work package five is situated on the innovation half opposite the research half which includes work packages one through three. Work package four delivers full sized stacks to work package five which implements these into a system and then processes it to a fully-fledged Fuel Cell System for work package six.

1.3 Scope

This document is the deliverable D5.4 from the work package 5. It is based on deliverables D5.1 (*Fuel-Cell System Interfaces*), D5.2 (*System Design*) and D5.3 (*Balance of Plant Components*).

The objective of this document is to describe the Fuel-Cell System assembly and commissioning. Relevant for the assembly are the requirements for the sub-system packaging of air, hydrogen, cooling and Electrical and Electronical (E/E) system. Depending on the choice of components and installation space, the assembly is key to a working system commission.

2 Overview of the System Topology

The trailer is a newly developed autonomous system used as range extender for the existing electrical bus (e-bus) developed by a collaboration between VDL, ElringKlinger (EK) and Bosch Engineering GmbH (BEG). All subsystems further specified below are controlled by the Fuel Cell Control Unit (FCCU) developed by BEG.

Figure 1 below shows the topology of the FC system in the trailer, including the hydrogen system in red, the air system in green and the cooling systems in blue, all shared by the two stacks. For maximum power output, the EK stacks are electrically connected in series.

Figure 1: Piping and instrumentation diagram of the Fuel Cell system for the range extender

The Piping and Instrumentation Diagram (P&ID) does not include legends or the depiction of the complete measurement environment. For this report the above P&ID can be used as reference for the component walk through of the packaging.

Also not shown in this D5.4 is the bus system topology, due to content overlap with previous work packages. The e-bus is a complete powertrain system consisting of inverter, e-motor, gearbox, High-Voltage (HV) battery with a nominal voltage of 600V, a Low-Voltage (LV) system at 24V and respective DC/DC converter and battery as well as further equipment allowing for connection with the HV system of the trailer. The bus system is independently controlled by the VDL Vehicle Control Unit (VCU).

3 System Responsibilities

Allocating specialized knowledge is standing to reason for dividing the responsibilities into three areas between the three partners VDL, ElringKlinger and Bosch Engineering.

3.1 VDL Responsibilities

The responsibilities of VDL lie with the trailer frame, the hydrogen system, part of the cooling system and electrical connections, power supplies and CAN communication between bus and trailer.

Table 1: VDL responsibilities classified as subsystems and appertaining details

System	Detail
Trailer frame	Including crash sensors and backlights
Hydrogen system	Including storage tanks, fueling and defueling system, pressure reducer and connecting pipes
Cooling system	Radiator hardware including fan and fan communication interface via pulse-width modulation (PWM)
Bus to trailer connection and communication	Electric bus (E-bus) including interlock plugs, 600V high voltage (HV) bus plugs for electrical connection, 24V power supply for backlights evading interference with the FC range extender and CAN communication connector for exchange of FC range extender signals

3.2 ElringKlinger Responsibilities

ElringKlinger supplies two 200-cell stacks providing power of up to 76 kW. The stack housing has integrated pressure release valves, jet pumps, water separators, purge and drain valves, pressure and temperature sensors for coolant input and cathode and anode outputs.

3.3 Bosch Engineering Responsibilities

Bosch Engineering provides auxiliary systems and components for those like the air system and the hydrogen system, cooling system, and electrical and HV components, auxiliary components as well as software and communication.

Table 2: BEG responsibilities classified as subsystems and appertaining details

System	Detail
Air system	Including air filter, compressor, intercooler, humidifier, cathode closing valves, throttle and bypass
Hydrogen system	Hydrogen gas injectors (HGI)
Cooling system	Including water pump, 3-way valve and heater
Electrical and HV system	12V battery and electrical system and Low Voltage (LV) DC/DC; HV contactors, auxiliary motor, HV DC/DC, and HV coolant heater
Auxiliary components	Sensors and actuators outside stack module and interlock lines outgoing from the trailer
Software and communication	Fuel Cell Control Unit (FCCU) hardware and software; CAN communication to related devices and E-bus and Vehicle Control Unit (VCU)

4 Requirements for System Packaging

Certain technical and physical requirements call for limitations in freedom for packaging.

4.1 Air System

The requirements for the air system primarily include the necessity for high-quality air and a dynamic cycle with little losses. The intake possibility for air within the trailer housing and appropriate filtering are prerequisites. Different components along the air path have therefore to be positioned correctly and not hinder the air flow and pressure build-up within the system.

4.2 Hydrogen System

Important for the correct installation of the hydrogen system is the positioning of any possibly leaking parts and components, as hydrogen has the strong tendency to quickly dissipate into the surroundings in an upwards direction. The responsibilities for the hydrogen system lie mainly with VDL which limits the influence assembly has on this particular subsystem. Even though the installation includes the hydrogen system, most components are already integrated in the stacks or hydrogen fuelling system.

4.3 Cooling System

A basic requirement for the cooling system is the purpose of cooling and therefore a thermodynamically thoughtful design. Additionally, in order to protect the stack and its life span, the cooling fluid should not interfere with the functionality of the stack and underlie the low electrical conductivity limits which might be affected by dimensioning.

4.4 E/E System

The requirements for the E/E system are, beside safety-related topics like protection against contact and correct isolation and cooling, not as relevant in terms of packaging. However, those topics are not to be fully ignored when assembling and commissioning the complete fuel cell system.

5 Fuel-Cell System Assembly

Leading on to the system assembly, it is easiest to perform a walkthrough of the system components and their positioning in order to evaluate the final packaging and its functionality. The requirements specified in section 4 *Requirements for System Packaging* are to be met by the final design solution.

Figure 2: side view (left) and bird view of back (right) of CAD package for the Giantleap trailer.

Figure 2 shows the packaging of the complete Computer Aided Design (CAD) of the FC system in the trailer as a range extender for the e-bus.

5.1 Air System

Figure 3 shows the CAD package for the Giantleap Air System. The numbers “(X)” are assigned to the respective component mentioned in the walk-through and will be referenced one at a time.

Figure 3: front view (left) and trimetric view (right) of CAD package for the Giantleap Air System.

Following the actual air path from intake through all components including the stack to the exhaust, a detailed reasoning is given for the majority of component installations.

Firstly, the air filter **(1)** is passed, which is mounted on the top left side. As the filter cleans the air by separation of particles from the cathode air and filters harmful or volatile organic compounds for protection of irreversible poisoning, wear and blocking of channels, it is important for the component to function correctly. In order to minimize air interference from too many surrounding components the free fitting on top has been chosen. This is also advantageous for practical reasons like changing the air filter.

Secondly, the Rotrex air compressor **(2)** is passed, which additionally accommodates auxiliary systems including an own cooling system requiring certain space. It is mandatory that the oil tank is positioned higher than the heat exchanger. As the compressor is tied to the e-motor SMG 180, the package is heavy. In order to ensure good drive dynamics, it is recommended to keep the centre of gravity as low as possible, leading to the compressor and above-mentioned components to be mounted at the bottom.

After the compressor the air is pushed through an intercooler **(3)** using water-air technology. For minimal throttle losses, short passages to the stack are better for the overall efficiency of the system. As the intercooler is a big component, it requires sufficient space. Also, it is the connection to the cooling system that is mounted on the other side of the trailer, hence requiring good access for the coolant pipes. For all these reasons the positioning was chosen as seen in Figure 2.

Following the intercooler, the air now passes through the humidifier **(4)** for the first time. As the air is dry and needs to be humidified, the component takes up additional passageway regarding throttle losses. However, after the humidifier the air is separated into two equally long pipes going into the stacks. It is important for the packaging that the two pipes have the exact same dimensions for proper and equal functionality of the cathode side of the stack.

The stacks **(5)** have been positioned in the top half of the left trailer side, as seen in Figure 2. This enables a good connection between the two stacks and the double voltage output by being electrically connected in series. Important is the joint assembly, as the two stacks work as one system sharing all subsystems and requiring good access for these systems to both stacks. As the stacks are heavy, they are positioned close to the tanks in the middle for drive dynamic reasons. Below, Figure 4 shows the assembly guidelines regarding the inclination angles for correct installation.

Figure 4: permitted deflection of the stack mounted in horizontal arrangement of the cells and with media connectors located at the lower end¹.

The humidifier **(4)** is passed a second time by the humid air coming from the stack. The air out pipes face downwards in order to collect produced residual waste water. This positioning is the best solution; however, it can also be changed in all axes' directions.

Next in the air path is a constellation of two valves. The first one is a bypass valve **(6)**, which is opened when starting up the system and allows the air from the intercooler to bypass the humidifier and stacks. Another rarer usage of the bypass is for pump protection regulating the air mass flow. The exit air instantly joins the exhaust air from the humidifier output to be passed through the next valve and then the silencer. Following the humidifier, the throttle valve **(7)** restricts the airflow in order to keep the overpressure in the system by increasing the exhaust gas back pressure. Assembly-wise, the two valves should be installed close to each other as solved in the Giantleap packaging.

¹ Manual for PEM fuel cell stacks of the series PEM NM5; Elring Klinger; 09/2016

Before exiting the air system, the exhaust air has to pass by a silencer **(8)** to counter the noise generation within the system. As the exhaust air also contains droplets of water, the silencer is installed vertically to prevent water collection.

Lastly, the exhaust air, containing amongst others hydrogen and water, is guided out at the top rear side **(9)** of the trailer for all previously mentioned reasons. Also, for obvious reasons, when moving the bus the exhaust gas can join the atmosphere in a quick and unobstructed manner.

5.2 Hydrogen System

Figure 5: trimetric view of CAD package for the Giantleap Hydrogen System.

Figure 5 is the CAD depiction of the hydrogen system. The tank and fuelling system is provided by VDL and is located in the centre of the trailer. Four tanks **(1)** with 8 kg hydrogen each at 350 bar pressure make up the heart of the hydrogen system.

A lot of the fuelling system is also incorporated in the stacks **(2)**. Therefore, the stacks are mounted directly next to the hydrogen tanks.

For safety redundancy, the VDL fuelling system includes an electrical shut-off valve SOV.05, a manual valve HV.11 and additionally an electrical shut-off valve SOV.30 controlled by the FCCU within the BEG scope. These components can be found in the P&ID in Figure 1.

5.3 Cooling System

Figure 6: trimetric view of CAD package for the Giantleap Cooling System.

With the right packaging and avoidance of lengthy piping, the thermodynamically motivated requirements could be met. Additionally, conductivity influences are kept to a minimum. Hence the cooling system is packaged closely and separately from the other systems. Also, the cumbersome fan needs enough surface facing the surroundings for maximum efficiency. These factors lead to the assembly as seen on the right side of the hydrogen tanks in Figure 2 and in above Figure 6.

5.4 E/E System

The LV and HV schematic has been delivered to VDL for the manufacturing of the trailer harness.

Figure 7: Topology of the E/E-System.

Figure 7 shows the simplified topology of the basic FC E/E-System for the Giantleap project. It includes the stacks, DC/DC converter, FC Output Box, InvCon Inverter and Motor.

Figure 8: side view (left) and trimetric view (right) of CAD package for the Giantleap E/E-System.

Figure 8 depicts the CAD package of the full E/E-System including numbering for all below mentioned components.

The E/E system is mostly dependent on the structure and assembly of the other subsystems. The HV DC/DC by Brusa **(1)** makes up the connection between the fuel cell stacks and the bus. It is quite cumbersome and heavy, resulting in a rather low positioning on the trailer's side, due to the required low centre of gravity. The HV inverter Invcon 2.3 **(2)**, with integrated DC/DC converter at 12 V level for the on-board power supply, is assembled with the Bosch e-motor and Rotrex compressor **(3)** in close proximity. A HV heater **(4)** is used for cold starts and any use case in which the system has to be brought to the required operating temperature; it is positioned to optimally heat the system.

The HV distribution between the stacks, HV DC/DC, Invcon and HV heater are positioned in the fuel cell output box **(5)**. The fuel cell output box is also BEG's responsibility, and has to be positioned on the trailer side facing the bus according to its purpose. Additionally, it accommodates fuses, HV switches, isolation monitoring and current measurement devices.

Furthermore, the E/E-System includes the fuse box **(6)**, a connector plug from the trailer to the bus **(7)**, a 3-way-valve **(8)** for heater use during cold starts and the stacks **(9)**.

5.5 Drain and Purge Lines

The drain and purge lines are mentioned separately due to their own requirements not entailed within the other subsystems.

Both lines are consolidated into one. They are mounted to the connective end plate on one side and join the exhaust system behind the silencer on the other. This prevents the humidity of the drainage to get caught in the silencer.

The two overpressure release valves PRV.11 and PRV.21 are also connected to the end plate, as they should lead directly to the exhaust exit due to safety reasons.

6 Fuel-Cell System Commissioning

The commissioning of the system has been successful as proven by tests.

Giantleap

Figure 9: Polarisation Curve of the Giantleap Stacks (average cell voltage and total stack power over current).

The three main operation points for the on-road FC system are at 20kW, 40kW and 70kW. The polarization curve, as seen in Figure 9, defines the relationship between the average cell voltage and the total current resulting in the overall stack power going through various points, including the three main points mentioned above.

6.1 System Implementation and Testing

In order to rely on a system to fully function, the initial implementation and testing is key. For the commissioning process tests need to be performed to investigate the functionality and cooperation of all subsystems.

6.1.1 Test Bench

The Giantleap system with all the final components has been implemented on a test bench. Packaging has yet to be tested on the road. Due to the possibility of more space and the necessity for easy access to all components in a testing environment, the spacing and assembly differs from the final packaging.

Figure 10: Picture of Giantleap system test bench in Schwieberdingen

However, the requirements stated in section 4 *Requirements for System Packaging* have been met and fulfilled, as seen in above Figure 10. The conditioning of the system and its subsystems led to further robustness of the software and hardware.

6.1.2 On-Road

The assembly for on road purposes has yet to be tested.

6.2 Commissioning Analysis

Concluding as stated in the beginning of section 6 *Fuel-Cell System Commissioning*, the system has been implemented successfully. The tests challenged a wide variety of operation points, and a case study during conditioning based on these points allowed for the on-road testing release. Also, the reference point for Beginning of Life (BoL) has been defined through the polarization curve. It will start with initial operation of the complete FC system in the on-road trailer setup.

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8 Table of Abbreviations

BEG	Bosch Engineering GmbH
BoP	Balance of Plant
CAD	Computer Aided Design
D	Deliverable
DC/DC	Direct current to direct current
EK	Elring Klinger
e-bus	Electric bus
E/E	Electrical and Electronical
FC	Fuel Cell
FCCU	Fuel Cell Control Unit
HV	High Voltage
LV	Low Voltage
PWM	Pulse Width Modulation
P&ID	Piping and Instrumentation Diagram
VCU	Vehicle Control Unit
WP	Work Package